

Effect of Systematic Desensitization Technique in Reducing Test Anxiety Among Secondary School Students in Anambra State

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Abstract

Test Anxiety constitutes serious academic impediments to lots of students in schools. It is considered to be one of the most common and widespread emotions for many students at all levels of education. This study investigated the effect of systematic desensitization technique in the reduction of Test Anxiety among secondary school students in Onitsha North Local Government Area. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Quasi-experimental research was adopted in carrying out the study. A sample size of 82 SSI students from coeducational schools was chosen from a population of 475 students with test anxiety. The sample was derived from two schools selected using purposive sampling technique based on the number of students that scored high on test anxiety. The instrument used for data collection was Spielberger's Test Anxiety Inventory. The instrument was reliable at 0.79 coefficients. Data relating to research questions were analyzed using statistical mean while data relating to hypothesis were analyzed using Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA). Findings from the study revealed that systematic desensitization technique was significantly effective in reducing secondary school students' test anxiety. It was also found that there was no gender difference in the effect of systematic desensitization technique on test anxiety among secondary school students who participated in the experiment. Based on the findings, it was recommended that systematic desensitization technique should be adopted as an effective treatment technique in treating secondary school students with test anxiety.

Keywords: *Effect, Systematic Desensitization, Technique, Test Anxiety, Students*

Introduction

In everyday life, human beings come across different things, issues and events that pose challenges to them. The way an individual perceives such challenges could generate diverse changes within the individual, which may lead to physiological, mental or emotional changes. Any of these changes if not properly controlled could result to anxiety in the individual. Globally,

tests are regarded as very important phenomena in schooling. Expectedly, students must take several tests in the course of their schooling as the results of such tests are essential for their academic actualization. One of the most extensive areas of research in the past few decades has been anxiety.

Anxiety may be defined as a feeling of unease, apprehension or worry which may be associated with physical symptoms such as rapid heartbeat, sweating and trembling. It is widely regarded as a global menace. According to Oluseyi and Olufemi (2015), anxiety is a general term for several disorders that cause nervousness, fear, apprehension and worry. Anxiety is said, to have occurred when one is being apprehensive of a situation and the reaction to such situation seems out of proportion compared with what might be normally expected (Obi & Oguzie, 2019). Anxiety triggers the physiological stress response, which can impede memory recall. It is a human reaction to any unknown situation and a pervasive problem with far reaching educational outcomes for many students.

According to Hopko, Crittendon, Grant and Wilson (2008), a student with high anxiety can fall behind academically because he or she is distracted and has impaired working memory skills when anxious. When one experiences too much anxiety, it can result in emotional or physical distress, difficulty in concentrating, and emotional worry (Vaez & Laflamme, 2008). Anxiety also affects cognition, motivation and the physiological makeup of the individual, it affects too the psychology and personality of normal person. The central characteristic of anxiety is worry, which is excessive concern about situations with uncertain outcome. Excessive worry is unproductive, because it may interfere with the ability to make action to solve a problem. Symptoms of anxiety may be reflected in thinking, behaviour or physical reactions (Neil & Christensen, 2009).

A good number of students experience anxiety during test which in most cases leads to poor performance in school. Test anxiety is an individual's physiological, cognitive, and behavioural responses that stimulate negative feelings about an evaluation. Oguzie, Ani, Obi and Onyegirim (2018) noted that when an individual becomes anxious, the physiological system becomes aroused, such as heart beating faster or the sweat glands producing more perspiration. At the same time, the individual may experience apprehension and a higher sense of inadequacy. When an individual experiences test anxiety, these physical and cognitive responses may lead to negative feelings and cognitions about testing situations. Too much anxiety over a test situation is commonly referred to as test anxiety (Bouras & Holt, 2007).

Egbochukwu, Obodo and Obadan (2008) observed that many secondary school students usually feel uneasy, fearful and anxious as tests approaches; some even go to the extent of feigning sickness. This anxious state of emotion exhibited by students towards test is what Spielberg (2006) referred to as test anxiety, and it constitutes serious academic impediments to students. Test anxiety can occur occasionally but when it becomes regular, it becomes a problem that cannot be overlooked.

Many students experience test anxiety, especially, in Nigeria where many tests are centralized and highly competitive. Tests are very important phenomena in schooling. Expectedly, students must take several tests in the course of their schooling as the results of such

as essential for a number of reasons. For instance, test such as the West African School Certificate, class examination or test are highly competitive and therefore stress the acquisition of knowledge at all costs by the students (Oguzie, Oguzie, Nnadi, Mokwelu & Obi, 2019). Also, the results are used to make important decisions about students and educational programs including grades, grade level promotions, honours, and graduation (Carter, 2006). Also educators and policy makers use test records to monitor students' learning progress and to assess the effectiveness of their progress and to assess the effectiveness of their instruction and identify ways to improve it (Salend, 2009).

Cassady and Johnson (2010) noted that between 25 to 40 percent of students experience test anxiety. They further stated that students who experience test anxiety tend to be easily distracted during test, experience difficulty in comprehending fairly simple directives and trouble organizing or recalling information. Such students usually end up failing a test when they have the required mental capacity to pass such test. These could be as a result of some factors such as parental pressure associated with greater worry, test irrelevant thoughts, and stronger bodily symptoms relating to anxiety during a test (Putwain, Woods & Symes, 2010). Others factors contributing to test anxiety of students, according to Anxiety Disorder Association of America (2012) include; fear of failure, procrastination, and previous poor test performance. Other characteristics of the test environment such as; nature of the task, difficulty, atmosphere, time constraints, examiner characteristics, mode of administration and physical setting could affect the level of anxiousness felt by the student (Putwain, Woods & Salend, 2012).

According to Test Anxiety Disorder of America (2012), test is often associated with loss of control, fear of failure, and both physiological and psychological reactions. The thought of writing test alone increases students stress and anxiety, no matter the extent of the preparation. Also, information from students interviewed shows that the environment inside the examination hall also has an effect on students test anxiety. Factors such as the sound of teachers alerting student on the remaining minutes to submit their examination scripts and the possibility of the scripts being collected without the students finishing the test have significant effect on increasing anxiety.

Test anxiety has much implication for many students at all levels of which failure in test is one of them. According to Zondi (2013), test anxiety can result in physiological, behavioural, and/or psychological effects. Physiological effects include rapid heartbeat, headache, tension, profuse perspiration; behavioural, which includes indecisiveness, being unable to organize thoughts; while psychological, involves feelings of nervousness, restlessness and continual doubt.

This prevalent problem of test anxiety reduces working memory, confuses reasoning, increases mistakes and lowers test score (Zondi, 2013). Researchers such as Onyekuru and Ibegbunam (2014) in their study reported further that between 25 to 40 percent of the students in secondary schools in Anambra state experiences test anxiety. According to them, Twenty percent of test-anxious students quit school before graduating because of repeated academic failure. Wang (2013) had earlier noted that 30 percent of students suffer from test anxiety and that high test anxiety is associated with low self-esteem, poor reading and poor performance in some

subjects; failing grades, disruptive classroom behaviours, negative attitude toward school, unpleasant feelings of nervousness and dread that stem from an intense fear of failure. Agreeing with the above, Chapell, et al (2009) similarly found a significant inverse relationship between test anxiety and grade point average among the students.

Test as a word evokes varying degrees of anxiety in students depending on the importance of the test, perceived difficulty level of the subject would elicit higher anxiety levels, and test anxiety as a psychological condition can adversely affect people in every field of life (Cohen, 2009), and especially it adversely affects students who face different test. Test anxiety for the purpose of this study is defined as physiological condition in which students experience intense fear, worry, and concern during tests. When secondary school students develop extreme fear for performing poorly on test, they usually experience test anxiety.

Putwain and Best (2011) examined the adjustment difficulties of high school students on test anxiety which have been an emerging issue. Many studies have proved that the adjustment difficulties on test anxiety are most evident in high school student. To help high school students in resolving their adjustment issues, efforts should be made in the form of establishing a counselling system to provide intervention to the students, so that their social and emotional problems did not interfere with their test performances.

Secondary school students, according to Putwain (2009) is a child in an intermediate school between primary school and university and usually offered general, technical, vocational, or university-preparatory subjects. For these students, test anxiety is a major factor contributing to a variety of negative outcomes, including psychological distress, academic underachievement, academic failure, and insecurity (Olorufemi & Akomolafe, 2013).

Test anxiety has been conceptualized in many ways leading to many methods of approaching its treatment. The research on test anxiety appears to have existed many decades but still continues today. It emerges as a multifaceted concept which engulfs different views centered on possible interventions. For instance, cognitive behavioural perspective suggests systematic desensitization technique as beneficial to students with test anxiety leading to positive test gain and improvement in academic tests (Driscoll, Holt & Hunter, 2008). Systematic desensitization technique has been shown to have effectively decrease anxiety levels in individuals who have difficulties relaxing in anxious situations (Larson, El Ramahi, Conn, Estes & Ghibellini, 2010; Obi & Oguzie, 2019). The meta- analysis conducted by Ergene (2006) on effective interventions on test anxiety reduction programme found behavioural and cognitive interventions to be effective in reducing test anxiety.

In spite of all these laudable efforts put in to reduce the frightening effect of test anxiety among students, test anxiety still remains a challenge and poses a serious threat to many students. This justifies the need to further explore other psychological techniques such as systematic desensitization in reducing students test anxiety. Hence, to reduce anxiety and other emotional maladjustment problems, series of psychological theories have been propounded and used (Oguzie & Nwokolo, 2019). These theories as pointed out by Smith (2006) have embedded in them counselling techniques which can be used in treating emotional disturbance, social

maladjustments, phobia and anxiety, among others. One of these techniques is Systematic Desensitization.

According to Ford (2008), systematic desensitization technique is a range of psychotherapeutic technique that is informed by the understanding of the behavioural and cognitive therapies which is focused on behaviours causing distress and changing irrational thoughts and beliefs. Systematic desensitization is a behavioural technique whereby a person is gradually exposed to an anxiety-producing object, event or place while being engaged in some type of relaxation at the same time in order to reduce the symptoms anxiety (Lazovik, 2013). Systematic desensitization uses learning theory and counter conditioning to effectively deal with a wide range of behavioural problems such as test anxiety. The study conducted by Bokanola (2014) on the effectiveness of systematic desensitization on the treatment of test anxiety found systematic desensitization to be effective towards having clients replace their anxious feelings with relaxation.

Rachman (2008) opined that the aim of systematic desensitization technique is to remove the fear response of phobia and substitute it with a relaxed response to the stimulus. This involves exposing the client to a low level of the anxiety producing stimulus and giving the strong version of the stimulus when the anxiety is no longer present. This is to say that the steps are repeated until the individual ceases to feel anxiety towards the stimulus. Moreover, Ventis, Higbee and Murdock (2013) reported a study where test anxiety was reduced using humor in systematic desensitization.

More so, test anxiety among students has been found to be significantly correlated with gender. Olisa and Sakin (2013) reported that test anxiety is more present in female students more than their male counterpart. Similarly, Akindele and Adeaga (2014) found that female students suffer from test anxiety more than the male students. However, Bassey, Peter and Omazagba (2014) had a contrary view on the gender difference in test anxiety. They reported that male students are more prone to test anxiety than their female counterpart.

The problem of test anxiety is still a major source of worry and unease to many students, parents, counsellors, teachers, and other well-meaning persons in the society. These stakeholders desire a solution to the test anxiety and it is time a definite answer is proffered. This has necessitated the need to use systematic desensitization technique in reducing test anxiety among students.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of systematic desensitization technique in reducing test anxiety among secondary school students. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. The effect of systematic desensitization technique on test anxiety among secondary school students when compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest scores.
2. The difference in the effect of systematic desensitization technique on the test anxiety among male and female students using their pretest and posttest scores.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of systematic desensitization technique on test anxiety among secondary school students when compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their pretest and posttest scores?
2. What is the difference in the effect of systematic desensitization technique on the test anxiety among male and female students using their pretest and posttest scores?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the effect of systematic desensitization technique on test anxiety among secondary school students when compared with those treated with conventional counselling using their posttest scores.
2. There is no significant difference in the effect of systematic desensitization technique on the test anxiety among male and female students using their posttest scores.

Method

The study adopted the non quasi experimental research design. According to Nworgu (2015), quasi-experiment is an experiment where a random assignment of subjects to experimental and control groups is not possible. In this case, intact or pre-existing groups are used. According to Asgari and Nunes (2011), quasi-experiment research is conducted in a natural setting rather than laboratory conditions, but in this design, variables are isolated, controlled and manipulated. The study was conducted in Onitsha North Local Government Area of Anambra State. The population of the study comprised of 475 students in senior secondary schools year one (SS1 students) from all the coeducational secondary school in Onitsha north local government area facing high level of test anxiety. The sample size of this study was 82 test anxiety students. This comprised of all SS1 students chosen from the two coeducational secondary schools selected for the study. The sample size was derived from the population of 475 students with high test anxiety scores from two coeducational secondary schools in Onitsha north local government area with the highest number of students with high test anxiety (using the pretest scores) served as the experimental groups I, II and III respectively.

The instrument used for measuring students' test anxiety was Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI). The instrument was originally developed by Spielberger (1972). The TAI is a self report psychometric scale which was developed to measure individual differences in test anxiety as a situation-specific trait. The test contains 20 items. Based on 4-point rating scale, ranging from 1 (almost never), 2 (sometimes), 3 (often), to 4 (almost always) (Spielberger, 1972). The respondents were required to indicate how frequently they experience specific symptoms of anxiety before, during and after examinations. In addition to measuring individual differences in anxiety proneness in exam situations, the TAI subscales assess worry and emotionality as major components of test anxiety. Coefficient alpha of 0.92 and higher has been reported for TAI (Spielberger, 1972).

All the senior secondary (SS1) students from all the coeducational secondary schools were given the Test Anxiety Inventory to complete. The researchers and six well trained research assistants went around the secondary schools to distribute 3,016 copies of the questionnaire. Each participant was met in their individual classes and were given the instrument TAI to respond to the items. The researchers gave the students an introductory instruction on how to complete the questionnaire. The nature of the student's responses and the purpose for which it served were clearly explained to the students. The researchers with the research assistants properly assisted and guided the students on how to respond to the questionnaire. The questionnaire sheets were collected from the students immediately they finished responding to the items and handed to the researcher for collation and scoring. Thus this was regarded as the pretest.

Each response was scored according to the specification on the TAI manual. Scores that were above the norm (34.77/ 34.37 for male and female and general norm of 34.86) indicated high level of test anxiety and scores below this showed no problem with test anxiety. This enables the researchers to identify test anxious students. These scores from the first administration of the questionnaire made up the pretest. A special request was made to the school principal for provision of adequate and conducive classroom for the administration of the treatment. After the six weeks experimental treatment and control group conventional group counselling, the instrument, TAI was re-administered on the students and this was regarded as the posttest. The responses were collated, scored and analyzed to determine statistical difference between the experimental and control group. Data related to the research questions were analyzed using Mean while data related to the null hypotheses were analyzed using Analysis of Co-variance (ANCOVA). The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Pretest and posttest test anxiety mean scores of students treated with systematic desensitization technique and those in the conventional counselling group (Norm = 34.86)

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Mean Lost	Remark
Systematic desensitization	43	61.21	30.93	30.28	Effective
Control	39	58.51	52.54	5.97	

Table 1 reveals that the students treated with systematic desensitization technique had pretest mean score of 61.21 and posttest mean score of 30.93 with mean lost of 30.28 in their test anxiety, while those in the control group who received conventional counselling had pretest mean score of 58.51 and posttest mean score of 52.54 with mean lost 5.97. With posttest mean score of 30.93 which is below the norm of 34.86, Systematic desensitization technique is effective in reducing test anxiety among the students.

Table 2: Pretest and Posttest Test Anxiety Mean Scores of Male and Female students treated with Systematic desensitization Technique (Norm = Male 34.77/Female 34.37)

Source of Variation	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Mean Lost	Remark
Male	20	61.15	30.40	30.75	No difference
Female	23	61.26	31.39	29.87	

Table 2 indicates that male students treated with systematic desensitization technique had pre-test mean score of 61.15 and post-test mean score of 30.40 with a mean lost of 30.75, while female students in the group had pre-test mean score of 61.39 and post-test mean score of 31.93 with mean lost of 29.87. Hence, systematic desensitization technique does not differ in its effect on male and female students' test anxiety.

Table 3: ANCOVA on the posttest test anxiety mean scores of students treated with systematic desensitization technique and those in the conventional counselling group.

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	9591.743	2	4795.872			
Intercept	2844.114	1	2844.114			
Pretest	42.751	1	42.751			
Treatmentmodel	9541.159	1	9541.159	86.15	0.00	S
Error	8749.732	79	110.756			
Total	157581.000	82				
Corrected Total	18341.	81				

Table 3 shows that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 81df denominator, the calculated F is 86.15 with Pvalue of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, the first null hypothesis is rejected. So, the effect of systematic desensitization technique in reducing test anxiety scores among secondary school students is significant.

Table 4: ANCOVA on the posttest test anxiety mean scores of male and female students treated with systematic desensitization technique

Source of variation	SS	df	MS	Cal. F	Pvalue	P ≤ 0.05
Corrected Model	23.381	2	11.690			
Intercept	1304.185	1	1304.185			
Pretest	12.869	1	12.869			
Gender	10.642	1	10.642	0.12	0.734	NS
Error	3627.410	40	90.685			
Total	44788.000	43				
Corrected Total	3650.791	42				

Table 4 reveals that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 42df denominator, the calculated F is 0.12 with Pvalue of 0.73 which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, the second null hypothesis is accepted. So, the difference in the effect of systematic desensitization technique on male and female secondary school students' test anxiety is not significant.

Discussion

The findings of this study revealed that systematic desensitization technique was effective on test anxiety among secondary school students as compared to those in the conventional counselling group. Specifically, the finding revealed that students in both systematic desensitization technique and conventional counselling groups exhibited test anxiety before the commencement of the study as measured by their scores on the pre-test. The findings also indicated that the magnitude of the mean difference between the systematic desensitization technique and conventional counselling groups was significant in the post-test.

Moreover, the systematic desensitization technique group reported a significant decrease in test anxiety than the conventional counselling group. This perhaps indicates that the students in the systematic desensitization technique group gained better understanding of their test anxiety as a result of receiving systematic desensitization training. This finding is consistent with prior researches that reported that systematic desensitization technique is effective on test anxiety among secondary school students (Larson, El Ramahi, Conn, Estes & Ghibellini, 2010; Bukola, 2013; Bokanola, 2014). In-line with this result of the study, Obi and Oguzie (2019) also observed that systematic desensitization technique was significantly effective in reducing anxiety among secondary school adolescents.

One likely reason for the decrease in test anxiety among students in the systematic desensitization treatment group than those in the conventional counselling group might be due to the anxiety counter conditioning training in which the students were exposed to, during the experiment. Supporting this, Lazovi (2013) noted that during systematic desensitization treatment, clients are gradually exposed to an anxiety-producing object, event or place while being engaged in some type of relaxation at the same time in order to reduce the symptoms anxiety. Systematic desensitization uses learning theory and counter conditioning to effectively deal with a wide range of behavioural problems such as test anxiety. This may therefore signify that the anxious feelings of the students during tests have been gradually replaced with relaxation and self assurance during the systematic desensitization technique treatment.

Another finding of this study is that there was no significant gender difference in the effect of systematic desensitization technique on secondary school students' test anxiety. The result from this study indicated that systematic desensitization technique does not differ in its effect in reducing test anxiety among the male and female students. This suggests that the male and female students benefited equally from systematic desensitization treatment. This finding supports the previous finding by Bokanola (2014) who observed that there is no gender difference in the effectiveness of systematic desensitization technique. This may be because both the male and female students were treated with the same systematic desensitization treatment package at the

same time and under the same condition. Moreso, the students were given equal opportunities to participate in the experimental activities and were also given equal attention.

However, this result contradicts previous finding by Bukola (2013) who reported that female students benefited more during systematic desensitization treatment than their male counterpart. Perhaps, Bukola did not maintain equilibrium of condition between the male and female students during his experiment.

Conclusions

This study investigated the relative effects of systematic desensitization technique on test anxiety among secondary school students. The study has confirmed previous researches that demonstrated the efficacy of systematic desensitization technique in reducing maladaptive behaviours among secondary school students. In accordance with the findings of this study, it was concluded that systematic desensitization technique was significantly effective in reducing secondary school students' test anxiety. It was also concluded that there was no gender difference in the effects of systematic desensitization on test anxiety among secondary school students who participated in the experiment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers made the following recommendations:

1. That systematic desensitization technique should be adopted by school guidance counsellors and other allied professionals as an effective treatment for helping test anxious students irrespective of their gender to improve their academic performance and test taking ability.
2. That counsellor's should practice different forms of relaxation techniques with students and provide them with the cognitive tools to defeat the negative self-talk they may experience before, during, and after the test. Governments and school administrators should give adequate support to counsellors and teachers alike, by providing conducive environment and giving adequate financial support to boost counselling activities in school.
3. That the Counselling association of Nigeria (CASSON) should create programs that will help sensitize Counsellors more on the use and benefits of systematic desensitization technique in treating test anxiety among secondary school students.

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